

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF THE ELASTIC CONSTITUTIVE BEHAVIOR OF A 2.5D INTERLOCK COMPOSITE

NEHME Samer^{*}, HAGEGE Benjamin^{*}, KAABI Abderrahmen^{**}, BENZEGGAGH Malk^{*}

^{*} Université de Technologie de Compiègne, Laboratoire ROBERVAL, UMR 6253

^{**} Centre des Matériaux, Mines Paris-ParisTech, CNRS 7633, Evry, France.

SUMMARY

This work is consisted to study a 2.5D braided composites provided by SNECMA Company. We thus propose a new meshing methodology to build an elementary volume made of tetrahedral for the isotropic matrix and of mapped hexahedra for the transversely isotropic yarns. The industrial software “Ansys” is used to solve this problem. Contact elements are generated to allow creating damages in our proceeding works inside the composite. The finite element model shows a good agreement with our experimental data.

Keywords: composite, interlock, finite elements, homogenization, elastic constitutive

INTRODUCTION

The understanding of the industrial need influenced by the technological advance in the composite materials field, led scientists to develop complex structures with good resistance in all directions. The “Aeronautical and aerospace” field is a good example. Unidirectional composites present a privileged resistance direction; they have a good strength in their longitudinal direction. Laminates, which are bidirectional composites, suffer from weakness in the third direction. Interlock is special textile composites in which mechanical properties are strongly related to its structure. Interlock’s geometry is so complex and the number of possible architectures is unlimited. The fabric architecture depends upon the undulation, crimp, and density of the fiber tows (untwisted strand of fibers). In the longitudinal direction, they are known as warp tows while in the cross direction, they are known as the fill ones or weft. The interlacing cause bending is called “tow crimp”. In the early models, the undulation in the warp direction was only taken into account [1]. Then more sophisticated models were created where they began to take undulation, not only in the warp direction, but also in the weft direction [2]. Moreover, they took the tows relative crimp into account.

In the following, a list of different types of models shows the variety of cases studied: Naik and Ganesh [3] developed 2D micromechanical models of plain weave fabrics to determine the elastic properties of the fabrics. They took the warp and weft tow undulation into consideration. In the case of the slice array model (SAM), the Representative Elementary Volume (RVE) was divided into several slices. Naik et al. [3] developed the element array model (EAM) in case of series-parallel (SP) and the parallel series (PS) models. Cox et al [4] and Xu et al. [5] developed a finite element model, referred to a binary model, to predict the mechanical properties of 3D interlock

composites. Huang [6] developed a micromechanical model to predict the elastic properties of the woven composites. In this case, tows were supposed to be elliptic and tows undulation was described by a sinusoidal function. Scida et al. [7] developed an analytical model called MESOTEX (Mechanical Simulation Of TEXTiles) based on classical laminated theory (CLT) to predict the 3D elastic properties, continuum damage evolution, and strength of woven fabric composites. In the approach of Barbero et al. [8], a finite element model of plain weave fabrics based on geometrical measurements from photographs was developed to determine the damage evolution using a meso-mechanical continuum damage formulation under tensile loading.

Up to now, limited attention has been focused towards understanding the mechanical behaviour of interlock composites. Although many models are available for predicting mechanical properties of interlock composites, each model has its limitations (i.e. the influence of the matrix in the determination of the mechanical properties). Further numerical simulations of such materials mainly involve geometrical models and automated tetrahedral meshes that make difficult to cope with the anisotropic constitutive behavior of tows. Therefore, the aim of this work is to develop accurate, finite element models of interlock to determine their mechanical properties without these limitations. Contact elements are generated to create damages in our proceeding works inside the composite. This work also aims to build an elementary volume made of tetrahedral for the isotropic matrix and of mapped hexahedra for the transversely isotropic yarns. The industrial software package “Ansys Academic Associate” is used to solve the problem with contact element, local orientation of the anisotropy in yarns and computation of nine macroscopic orthotropic engineering constants. Comparisons are presented with the experimental results.

CONSTRUCTION OF THE REV

In surface this reinforcement resembles to taffeta fabric. The samples for this reinforcement are located by the number 69 according to the supplier. Figure1 shows the architecture of the interlock on surface. Two successive warp tows are shifted of one arranged of screen according to a vertical plan.

Figure 1: top view of reinforcement

This reinforcement belongs to the family of 2.5D layer-to-layer angle interlock. A microscopic observation of tows sections shows their elliptic form [9]. These flattened elliptic sections are geometrically modeled by a rectangle and scaled ellipses that vary with respect to the geometrical dimensions of tows.

Figure 2: microscopic observations and modeling of tows sections

The microscopic observation helped us, also, to define the architecture of the reinforcement (geometrical and dimensions) related to the structure. These dimensions are defined in the following table1.

Table 1: Geometrical parameters of reinforcement

Warp tows		Weft tows		distance between tows	
Width	Thickness	Width	Thickness	Weft tows	Warp tows
a_w (mm)	h_w (mm)	a_f (mm)	h_f (mm)	C_L (mm)	C_T (mm)
4.4706	06471	3.163	0.5882	2.8235	0

The REV of reinforcement consists of two Warp tows direction (the vertical plans) and of four Weft tows direction. In this particular REV, each layer in the vertical plan is made by three Warp tows direction and each layer in the horizontal plan made by two Weft tows direction.

The REV must be reliable on its representation's level for total mechanical behavior of the reinforcement. The objective is to define a simple geometrical volume which can represent the reinforcement and supports a hexahedral meshing.

Figure 3: Dimensions and architecture of the REV

Figure 3 illustrates dimensions of the REV where it's clearly showed the stacking in the two directions of tows. These dimensions are given in millimeter. The warp direction is made of two zones: the first one where the tow is curved and remains always tangent to the surface of the weft direction, and the second one where the tow is linear. The last zone is limited by two points from which the warp direction leaves the weft direction towards the other weft.

The creation of the 1/4 of the section leads to a quadratic meshing of good quality. Building a surface that accepts a quadratic meshing return to obtain a structure accepts a hexahedral meshing in the 3D. To succeed, it is enough to extrude the section according to the curve defines by the pace of the tow (figure 4).

Figure 4: Warp creation

The purpose of this study is to propose a simple geometrical volume which represents this reinforcement and supports a hexahedral meshing. We ensure coincidence between the nodes of the triangular elements (skin of the tetrahedral matrix) and the quadrangular elements (skin of the hexahedral tows) (figure 5). To find the suitable global size of the mesh, a sensitive analysis with several REV is made.

Figure 5: meshing of the VER (coincidence of the nodes)

The structure of the reinforcement presents a particular geometry. Indeed, the REV has two vertical symmetry planes (according to plans XZ and YZ). This is why we have considered the 1/4 of REV (figure 6) in determining the reinforcements' mechanical properties in the three directions, always with respect to some boundary conditions.

Figure 6: Assembly of tows and matrix

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The matrix ensures the connection between tows. In the case of our interlock, the matrix is into epoxy. The resins epoxy is used in the industry of high efficiency like aeronautics. It presents a good fixing on fibers and a weak withdrawal to moulding ($\approx 0.5\%$). The mechanical characteristics of this thermo hardening polymer are summarized in table 2:

Table 2: Mechanical properties of matrix

<i>Young modulus E_m (Mpa)</i>	Poisson's ratio ν_m	<i>shear modulus G_m (Mpa)</i>
<i>3500</i>	<i>0.4</i>	<i>1250</i>

A tow is an association of long fibers and resin that's their characteristics combine with synergy. A tow can contain approximately 10,000 fibers.

The tows used are called T300J according to the supplier. The fibers are out of carbon and the resin out of epoxy. They are modelled like unidirectional composite, and in consequence, the law of mixture is applicable. Table 3 presents the mechanical characteristics of carbon fiber high strength [10].

Table 3: mechanical properties of a carbon fiber

Longitudinal Module E_{f_l} (Mpa)	Transversal Module E_{f_t} (Mpa)	shear modulus $G_{f_{lt}}$ (Mpa)	Poisson's ratio $\nu_{f_{lt}}$	Poisson's ratio $\nu_{f_{tz}}$
<i>230000</i>	<i>15000</i>	<i>50000</i>	<i>0.28</i>	<i>0.03</i>

The mechanical characteristics of tows are calculated using the mixture equations' law. The results are grouped in the following table 4:

Table 4: Mechanical parameters of tows

Volume fraction of carbon fibers / REV (%)	60
Volume fraction of carbon fibers / Tows Vf (%)	78,25
(1-Vf) (%)	21,75
E_L (Mpa)	180396.5
E_T (Mpa)	8516.4
E_Z (Mpa)	8516.4
G_{LT} (Mpa)	5272,8
G_{LZ} (Mpa)	5272,8
G_{TZ} (Mpa)	4246,7
V_{LT}	0,306
V_{LZ}	0,306
V_{TZ}	0,03

To ensure the elements' material orientation in the tows, all the elements of the same group have the same connectivity. The industrial package "Ansys Academic Associate" makes it possible to visualize the local orthotropic constitutive axes on each element.

The properties determined previously are in the principal direction of the tows as it is assembled on figure 7.

Figure 7: Orientation according to the direction of tows

CONTACT ELEMENT, BOUNDARY, AND PERIODICITY

To model the interfaces “Tows - matrix” and “Weft Tows – Warp Tows”, contact elements are generated (figure 8). The contact is a tied one. According to the birth and death approach, damages are created inside the composite.

Figure 8: zones of contacts

In a static problem, the boundary conditions must be employed to prevent the model from moving in any direction. We applied to each stage the boundary conditions necessary to maintain the structure in a state of balance. Then we imposed conditions of periodicity on the REV that can be applied by using constraint equation in ‘ANSYS’. However, periodicity conditions are not easy to apply to FEM discretizations when we generate a free-mesh, because nodes on opposite sides of the RVE cannot be found in pairs with two identical coordinates.

RESULTS

Tensile tests are made in the three spatial directions to determine the three elastic modulus and the associated three Poisson’s ratio. Shear rail tests are also made to determine the three shear modulus. The total deformation shows that the numerical REV follows the experimental results well. In traction along the Y axis (warp tows

direction) we find an error out of 0.44%. The results are grouped in the following table 5.

Table 5: Results

	% C /REV	Ex (Gpa)	Ey (Gpa)	Ez (Gpa)	Gxy (Gpa)	Gxz (Gpa)	Gyz (Gpa)	Vyx	Vxz	Vyz
Experimental	60	**	45,1	**	**	**	**	0.16	**	**
ABAQUS	60	20,2	47.1	7.9	**	**	**	**	**	**
ANSYS	60	18.2	45.3	9.7	6.4	8.6	4.8	0.14	0.24	0.17

The first calculation uses the software ‘ABAQUS’ [11], after that a second one also uses ‘ANSYS’ but this time adding periodicity condition and contact element to obtained a better result.

EFFECT OF MATRIX

If the matrix is removed, one notices an important decrease of elasticity modulus in X and Z axis of 69% and 72% respectively. According to X direction only one tow reacts to traction. In Z direction the linear part of the warp tows reacts to traction while the curve part cannot react. On the contrary in the Y direction all the wefts resist traction. That’s why we don’t have a great decrease (just 6%). The traction in Y direction allows us to observe the influence of the resin on the material’s mechanics properties which have limited influence. Its role is to ensure the bond between fibers and to distribute the efforts in the REV. the following table 6 resume the effect of matrix.

Table 6: role of the matrix

	Ex (Gpa)	Ey (Gpa)	Ez (Gpa)
With matrix	18.2	45.2	9.7
Without matrix	5.5	42.5	2.7
% of decrease	69.6%	6.1%	72.2%

DAMAGE MODEL

Many modes of damage can be observed in composite materials, including matrix crack, fiber-matrix de-bonding, fiber breakage, and many more. The analysis of composite structures may require the construction of damage models capable of predicting the different damage mechanisms and their evolution until fracture. One notable damage effect is a reduction of stiffness which can be used to define damage. The objective in this part is to model the damage mechanisms of the interfaces tows/matrix and Warp/Weft in the reinforcement. Finite elements Modeling of the damage is a mesoscopic scale. Numerical cracks were creating according to the appearance and

propagation mechanisms. We used an analysis method of delamination in the composites' structure with interlock reinforcement. This allows us to describe the influence of the size of the initial crack on the total rigidity. Indeed, we have created numerical cracks concentrated in specific places, followed by digital simulation and comparisons with the results obtained without damage. The microscopic observation in the block of the composite with interlock reinforcement shows the release of cracking's which takes place in the interfaces of block resins with the warp tows [9]. The stages of the appearance, propagation and rupture are illustrated in the figure 9.

Figure 9: Mechanism of the rupture in the composites with interlock reinforcement

In the numerical model, the contacts Tows/Matrix and Warp/Weft are defined in the chart of the interactions like tied contacts. 'Ansys' manages and models the contact between two surfaces joined together within a pair of contact element always bonding. The maintain force is strongly dependant on surface of the contact. In other words, if we reduce the intervening number of elements in this contact, the rigidity of the interface is decrease. In this spirit, we erased some elements contact Warpi/Weftj and we analyzed the effect on the reinforcement's rigidity. The minimal size of a crack is equal to element size. The meshing carried out on this reinforcement makes it possible to introduce damage around 200 μ m. We carried out ten experiments with a size of increasing crack. Table 7 summarizes these experiments. The cracks are localized in the places explained by the experimental given.

Table 7: Experimental procedures of the damage creation

	Number of lines eliminated by interface	Full number of the elements eliminated in the REV
Exp 1	1	92
Exp 2	2	184
Exp 3	3	276
Exp 4	4	368
Exp 5	5	460
Exp 6	6	552
Exp 7	7	644
Exp 8	8	736
Exp 9	9	828
Exp 10	10	920

It is important to announce that in experiment 10, we eliminated all elements intervenes in the contact at the places of cracks localization. Figure 10 studies the places where we have introduced the damages.

Figure 10: localization of damages

DAMAGE RESULTS

We present in the table 8 the results of the damage analysis.

Table 8: Results of damage analysis

Damage	Ex (Gpa)	Ey (Gpa)	Ez (Gpa)
Without damage	18.26	45.2	9.8
damage 1	18.23	45.1	9.7
damage 2	18.21	45	9.6
damage 3	18.11	44.9	9.5
damage 4	18.01	44.8	9.45
damage 5	17.81	44.6	9.4
damage 6	17.5	44.5	9.2
damage 7	17.3	44.3	8.9
damage 8	17.2	44	8.6
damage 9	17.1	43.8	8.3
damage 10	17	43.1	7.7

The introduction of the cracks into the numerical model generates a fall of the mechanical properties. For 0.2 mm damage, we observe a reduction in the rigidity of 0.15% in X direction, of 0.19% in Y direction and 0.12% in Z direction. If the size of the internal defect increases about 2mm, the module of elasticity in directions X and Y decrease of 6.1% and 3.87% respectively, whereas the modulus of elasticity in direction Z decrease of 20.3%.

CONCLUSION

This study approached the modeling of the mechanical behavior of a composite material with carbon interlock reinforcement. The elastic properties' determination was made using a numerical model also the modeling of damage was taken into consideration while using contact elements. This study reveals the importance of the chosen REV and meshing on certain mechanical properties. The numerical model suggested was validated following a comparison with the experimental tests. Moreover rigidities depend on the possible damages; they are given in three directions and compared with undamaged rigidities.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge Pr. Zoheir ABOURA for his collaboration to the experimental part.

References

- [1] Ishikawa et al. 82[11] Ishikawa T, Chou TW. Stiffness and strength behavior of wove fabric composite. *J Mater Sci* 1982;17:3211–20.
- [2] Aboura Z., Chouchaoui C.S., Benzeggagh M.L. (1993), « Analytical model of woven composite laminate superposition effect of two plies », *Congrès ECCM 6 EACM*, Bordeaux, 1993.
- [3] Naik NK, Ganesh VK. Prediction of on-axes elastic properties of plain weave fabric composites. *Compos Sci Technol* 1992;45:135–52.
- [4] B.N. Cox, W.C. Carter, N.A. Fleck, *Acta Metall. Mater.* 42 (1994) 363–379.
- [5] J. Xu, B.N. Cox, M.A. McGlockton, *Acta Metall. Mater.* 43 (1995) 3511–3524.
- [6] Huang ZM. The mechanical properties of composites reinforced with woven and braided fabrics. *Compos Sci Technol* 1999;60:479–98.
- [7] D.Scida, Z.Aboura, M.L.Benzeggagh et E.Bocherens, « *Amicromechanics model for 3D elasticity and failure of woven-fibre composite materials* », 1998.
- [8] E.J. Barbero, J. Trovillion, J.A. Mayugo, K.K. Sikkil, “Finite element modelling of plain weave fabrics from photomicrograph measurements” , *Composite Structure* 73 (2006), pp. 41-52.
- [9] Christiane HAGE, Thèse « Modélisation du comportement élastique endommageable de matériaux composites à renfort tridimensionnel », Université de Technologie de Compiègne, 2006.
- [10] Daniel GAY, « *Matériaux composites* », 4 eme édition, HERMES, Paris, 1997.
- [11] KAABI Abedrrahmen « Modélisation par éléments finis du comportement mécanique des composites à renforts 2,5 D », France, 2007.